

Portrayal of Women in the Novels of Chitra Banerjee Dinakaruni

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Abstract

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni is an indo- American writer. She has won many accolades and awards. Divakaruni's writing often centers on around the lives of women she writes about their pain and their feelings. She shows the experience of women their struggles, in trying to find personal identities women in particular respond to Divakaruni's work. The female characters in the fiction of Divakaruni are torn between old and new world values.

Keywords: Gender, Feminism, Identity social inequalities immigrant.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni, one of the Indian diasporic writers defines the status of women in contemporary times. "Independence with social acceptance success and autonomy that set its boundaries but do not require a complete break from the traditional extended semi- feudal family structure."

Woman of the contemporary times is dynamic. She knows her aspirations in life and at the same time plays an important role in family and society changing the lives of other women around her. She is able to explain new possibilities of enjoying success in the larger society beyond the traditional conventions and behavior she is ascribed it. It is fact to be acknowledged that she has become emotionally, psychologically physically, economically and politically strong in the present day. No longer in the need for her to be submissive and subservient in the male-dominated world. Since India is a conservative and traditional society bound by moral conventions. It has become a little tough to find a place of her own. Despite all these pressures and pulls, a woman is able to prove her mettle in every field. She is also able to assert her individuality and independence. Many Indian women novelists, I have explored female subjectivity in order to establish an identity that is not imposed by a patriarchal society. A number of Indian Women novelists made their debate, producing novels which revealed the true state of Indian society and its treatment of women. The image of women in fiction has undergone a change during the last four decades woman writers have moved away from traditional portrayals of enduring self.

Sacrificing women toward conflicted female character searching for identity no longer characterized and defined simply in terms of their victim status. Recent writers depict both the diversity of women and the diversity within each woman, rather than limiting the lives of women to one ideal. The novels emerging in the 21st Century furnish examples of whole range attitudes towards the impositions of tradition, some offering an analysis of the family structure and the caste system as the key element of patriarchal social organization.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni gives more importance to women characters. In her novels she has explored the physical and psychological tensions and tortures to which the women are subjected. She has represented women as actively upholding and shaping class culture and gender structures within the community, home and marriage she deals with the lives of women both at home and abroad. She writes about their pain and their feelings. She shows, the experience of women their struggles in trying to find personal identities. Women in particular respond to Divakaruni's work, because she is working like them, women in love in difficulty women in relationship. Women who doom themselves and most of this misery comes directly or indirectly at the hands of Indian men husbands whom the women perceive to be insensitive boors or worse.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's novel the "The Mistress of spices" presents the inner sorrows of the lives of the Indian women. It shows the Tilo's oscillation between personal responsibilities and social relationships. Tilo a magical figure who runs a grocery store and uses spices to help the customers overcome difficulties. In the process she develops dilemma of her own, when she falls in love with a non-Indian. There is a feeling of rootlessness alienation and marginalization on the part of the character of Tilo in "The Mistress of spices". It is well structure so as arrive how the women characters in Divakaruni's novel encounter immigrant issues within the frame work of the Indian sensibilities.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni draws an extraordinary portrait of Indian women who flout own terms. Women in Sister Of My Heart are not Stereotypes of wife-mother-housewife though steeped in Indian culture and moral values. The search as identity is much pronounced in the character of Sudha. Sudha likes a "Good Indian girl settles for arranged marriage". She agrees to

make everyone happy by this negotiated marriage. Soon she realizes the emptiness of this kind of life. The pressure of her mother-in-law forces her to analyse her life. She realizes that she is effacing life. She is under constant pressure to give a heir to the family a son. She was struggling with her husband and mother in law to save her un-born baby. Even though her mother in law is a female she cannot understand the feelings and love of a mother. This is the cry of a woman for her place in society. But the voice of woman could not be heard by the men. Chitra Banerjee examines the men in which woman is economically socially or politically oppressed in the society and how she breaks away from the constantly of the society. She is able to present the essential female qualities. She portrays the position of woman in society and also the ambition, fears and anxieties of the modern woman.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni "The place of illusions" is well known to all but the fascination of this novel lies in the unique way in which a female looks into the world, observes it and how the world confines the space for female. The author makes an attempt to place the woman in the forefront of the action". The novel "The place of illusions" is a kind of retelling of the epic from Draupadi's point of view Draupadi is swept into their quest to reclaim their birth right, remaining at their side through years of exile and terrible civil war involving all the important kings of India.

Draupadi is fiery female redefining for us a world of warriors, God and the ever manipulating hands of fate. She married to five males but could not get these things in her own way Pandavas gave her own palace but that palace proved an illusion for her life, illusion that she is safe an illusion that she is mistress of that palace, illusion that nobody can harm her in her personal domain. In the novel "The Place of Illusions" female Character like Kunti Amba or Shikhandi Gandhari were very powerful and strong ladies in their roles though they have to suffer a lot in the male dominating society. Divakaruni very thoughtfully discloses the different layers of patriarchal system and struggles of female characters who fights for honor and dignity.

In the novel Oleander girl the story focuses women's issues family secrets Hindu and Muslims clashes traditional is new India Divakaruni who is an Indian English women author has tried to give is an idea about all those type cast which are related to the inferiority of women.

The women Characters of Divakaruni see a change in their lives have self-perception and perception of others in family and society. They emerge as new women who work and live with new spirit some to her women characters try to walk out of marriage; others seek reunion thinking understanding and realizing their mistakes. It is a different kind of liberation there women try to experience.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni focuses the diaspora Indian women caught between two opposing worlds. Various problems and frustration faced by the diaspora women are projected through her women characters. They find themselves in an in between state struggling to carve out identities of their own. Divakaruni depicts both old and new generation of immigrant women with different gender problems.

Divakaruni's women characters see themselves differently from earlier roles they had played. There is transformation in her female characters, are powerful enough to create wars. They need freedom and self-actualization she has represented women as actively upholding and shaping class cultural and gender structures within the community, home and marriage she deals with lives of women both at home and abroad. Divakaruni's women are powerful but envision their powers working more brilliantly after the struggles and problems they experienced. A women who discovers and understands herself can liberate herself from the difficulties she experiences. She emerges to be a new woman with full grown attenuates and can freely exercise her autonomy. It is a joyous phase in a woman's life, if she is capable of liberating herself from unpleasant situations. Thus Divakaruni's main aim and message she desires to convey is that women need to understand themselves, their status and position and need to be independent and assertive. So, It is a work of women, for the women, by the women.

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